

Studies on the Interaction of Metal Ions and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Proteins. Part II. Interaction of Cobalt, Nickel, Silver, and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Gelatin

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pH-metric titrations of anionic gelatin with cobalt, nickel, and silver salts have shown that these metal ions become bound with the amino groups of the protein. Titrations could be extended to pH ranges beyond those for the onset of precipitation of their hydroxides. The combining powers are in the order: Ag(I) > Ni(II) > Co(II). Unlike alumina, pH-metry fails to supply information regarding the binding of the metal ions of the hydrrous oxide sols although inflections in the viscosity-concentration curves provide evidence in favour of complex formation between the sol and the protein (probably adsorption complex).

In the previous communication¹ we could get enough evidence of the binding of aluminium ions by gelatin while investigating the interaction of alumina sol of pH 1.7 with anionic gelatin. It was also observed that unlike aluminium, ferric ions, either from the ferric hydroxide sol or its corresponding salt, did not undergo complex formation with the amino-acid residues of the protein. On the other hand, binding with the hydrogen ions from the electrical double layer was found to be possible.

The present communication deals with the interaction of Co(II), Ni(II), and Ag(I) with gelatin by carrying out pH-metric and viscometric studies under exactly similar conditions employed in the case of Fe(III) and Al(III). These seem to differ from the latter investigations in two ways: (i) Nitrogen instead of oxygen of the protein offers site for metal binding. (ii) Viscometric studies provide information regarding the complex formation (adsorption) between the sol and gelatin inspite of the fact that no such evidence on the basis of pH-metry could be made available.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrolyte solutions were prepared by dissolving A. R. samples of cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, and silver nitrate in double distilled water. Solutions of gelatin (conc. 1%, pH 12.00) and that of NaOH of the same pH were prepared as described in the previous communication¹.

Hydrrous oxide sols of cobalt and nickel were prepared by excessive washing of the freshly prepared hydroxide precipitate according to the method of Tower and Cook². Silver oxide sol was prepared by the method recommended by Lottermoser.³ The concentra-

1. *This issue*, p. 693.

2. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 733.

3. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1905, ii, 72, 39.

tions of cobalt oxide, nickel oxide, and silver oxide were found to be 0.731g, 3.813g, and 8.552g./litre respectively. Their respective pH values were 7.6, 7.8, and 8.2; sols in the pH range lower than these could not be prepared. When examined by Burton's type electrophoretic tube, all of them were found to be positively charged. The pH of the electrolyte was brought as far as possible to these pH s by adding requisite amounts of alkali. The concentrations of cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, and silver nitrate were, $4.48 \times 10^{-2} M$, $4.21 \times 10^{-2} M$, and $5.88 \times 10^{-2} M$ respectively.

pH measurements were carried out as before by means of a Cambridge pH meter (bench type) using a glass electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode.

Varying volumes, viz.; 0, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, and 15 ml of cobalt chloride and cobalt oxide sol (pH 7.5), nickel chloride and nickel oxide sol (pH 7.6), silver nitrate (pH 6.8), and silver oxide sol (pH 8.2) (sol of pH near about 6.8 could not be prepared) were taken in 50 ml pyrex conical flasks. Two sets were arranged containing 5ml of 1% gelatin or NaOH solution (pH 12.00) making the total volume 20ml in each case. The results are shown in Figs. 1-3. Coagulation did not take place when sols were treated with gelatin solution. NaOH precipitated sols as well as the electrolytic solution. On treating anionic gelatin with the electrolytes, it was found that cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, and silver nitrate could be titrated to pH 9.5, 10.0, and 10.7 respectively without precipitation. The pH of the mixtures was determined after 24 hours in each case.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

A=sol+gelatin. B=sol+NaOH. C=electrolyte+gelatin. D=electrolyte+NaOH.

Viscometric measurements of the mixtures were carried out at a constant temperature (25°) under identical conditions using modified Scarpa's method⁴. The results are shown in Fig. 4 in the form of a plot between volume of the sol and specific viscosity.

DISCUSSION

The pH -titration curves for the solutions of cobalt, nickel, and silver salts show a close resemblance as far as the shift in the pH and the pH range, in which it occurs, are concerned (curve C, Figs. 1-3). In all the three cases the electrolyte-gelatin curve lies above the corresponding curves for the alkali (curves C and D, Figs. 1-3), thereby indicating a possible combination of the metal ions with the protein. Another striking feature

4. *Gazzetta*, 1910 40, 271; Prasad *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1384.

about these titrations is that the titration could be extended to quite high pH values (silver, pH 10.7; nickel, pH 10; cobalt, pH 9.5) in presence of gelatin without the precipitation setting in. This observation therefore goes to show that the protein competes with its free base in combining with the metal ions to such an extent that upper limit (ranging between pH 8 and 9.5 for the ions under investigation) for the onset of the precipitation as hydroxide is easily crossed. Further confirmation could be found from the fact that in this region (pH 9.2-10.7) salting out of the protein did not occur—a behaviour which could only be ascribed to some sort of combination between the protein and the metal ions.

Unlike alumina, colloidal solutions of the hydrous oxide of cobalt, nickel, and silver do not bring about shift in pH . On the other hand, the curves for the three sols and gelatin almost coincide with those for the sol and $NaOH$ (curves A and B, Figs. 1-3). The results on viscosity measurements, however, are in variance with those obtained from pH -metry. Here it is found that marked variation in viscosity takes place on adding gradually increasing amount of the sols to gelatin. Besides, sharp inflections are observed in the viscosity curves for nickel and cobalt (Fig. 4, curves *a* and *b*) indicating an aggregation due to the reaction between the metal ions and the protein. Here a reaction between the metal ions from the inner part of double layer with the reactive sites of the protein, based on chemical combination, is not feasible. But since a marked change in viscosity, accompanied by a definite inflection in the viscosity-concentration curves, takes place, some sort of quantitative relationship during the interaction can be visualised. In all probability it may be due to the formation of adsorption complex.

FIG. 4

Some light on the type of binding taking place between the metal ions and the protein can be thrown by considering the pH s to which the shift in the titration curves

occurs. Since these values lie in the range, where the reactivity of the ϵ -amino groups of gelatin is quite likely, it can safely be concluded that the metal ions co-ordinate through the nitrogen of the amino-acid residues of gelatin. Moreover, the relative shifts in the titration curves show that the combining power of the metals for the protein is of the order: Ag (I) > Ni (II) > Co (II). Further work with transfusion gelatin is in progress.

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